

THE PECULIARITIES OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Mamutova Shoxista Mohmudjonovna

EL teacher, School № 8 Urgench city, Khorezm region

Eshmetova Adolat Alimjanovna

EL teacher, School № 17 Gurlen district, Khorezm region

Annotation: the given article deals with the peculiarities of foreign languages. Here is also given benefits of learning a foreign language, useful tips which are really helpful and information to get.

Key words: foreign language, learning foreign languages, benefits of foreign languages.

A foreign language is a language not commonly spoken in the country of the speaker . However they must be a defined distinction between foreign language and second language. It is also a language not spoken in the native country of the person referred to, for example a German speaker living in the Philippines can say that Filipino is a foreign language to them or a Russian speaker living in China can say that Chinese is a foreign language to them. These two characterizations do not exhaust the possible definitions, however and the label is occasionally applied in ways that are variously misleading or factually inaccurate.

Some children learn more than one language from birth or from a very young age then they are bilingual or multilingual. These children can be said to have two, three or more mother tongues: neither language is foreign to that child, even if one language is a foreign language for the vast majority of people in the child`s birth country. For example, a child learning English from his English father and Irish at school in Ireland can speak both English and Irish, but neither is a foreign language to them. This is common in countries, such as Canada and Singapore due to these countries having multiple official languages.

In general, it is believed that children have advantages to learning a foreign language over adults. However, there are studies which have shown adult students are better at foreign language learning than child students. It is because adults have pre-existing knowledge of how grammar works and a superior ability of memorizing vocabulary.

Foreign languages provide a competitive edge in career choices: one is able to communicate in a second language. Foreign language study enhances listening skills and memory. One participates more effectively and responsibly in a multi-cultural world if one knows another language.

The advantages of learning foreign languages are mushrooming as the world becomes increasingly globalised and bilingualism is now perhaps the most useful real world skill to ever exist, rather than just being a nifty party trick. If you are thinking about making the effort to learn a foreign language rather than expecting the world to accommodate your monolingualism, you are a rare breed indeed. Blossoming into the impressive polyglot you aspire to be 100% feasible with the right approach and mindset.

Foreign language study is all about learning how to truly communicate and connect with others – an incredibly important life skill that can only be cultivated by interacting with people. When you master a foreign language, you can exercise your new superhuman power of being able to understand what someone is saying, recall the proper vocabulary and grammar, put that vocabulary and grammar, into the proper context and reply back – all on the spot and in a timely manner. You have connected. And that is what it is all about.

There are a lot of benefits of learning foreign languages:

- Boots brain power.
- Improve memory.
- Enhances the ability to multi-task.
- Sharpens the mind.
- Keeps the mind sharper for longer.
- Enhances decision-making.
- The first language is improved.
- Improves performance in other academic areas.

Nowadays the need for specialists with a high level of foreign language training for personal and professional communication is growing due to the intensive development of international cooperation.

There are many technologies in language training of technical university students but due to the analysis the modular technology is considered to be the most effective in the aspect of foreign language training.

References:

1. Chappelle C & Hegelheimer. V (2004), The English Language teacher in the 21st century. New Perspectives on CALL for second language classrooms. NY: Mahwah.
2. www.researchgate.net
3. www.sciencedirect.net

